

Electrochemical Reduction Behaviour of 1-Amino-9,10-anthraquinone

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The electrochemical reduction behaviour of 1 amino-9,10-anthraquinone has been studied by employing d.c. polarography cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography and differential pulse polarography in the supporting electrolytes of pH ranging from 2.0 to 12.0. Millicoulometry is employed for the determination of number of electrons involved in the electrode process. Diffusion coefficient values and forward rate constant values are evaluated. The nature of the electrode process and reduction mechanism have been presented. In this communication a detailed polarographic determination procedure has been described, based on the well-defined cathodic peaks obtained for the electroactive species.

Anthraquinones sustain biological electron transfer chains located in the membranes of mitochondria, bacteria and chloroplasts¹. The biochemical functions of quinones are connected to a great extent with their ability to undergo reversible redox conversion and therefore the investigation of their electrochemical properties has aroused significant interest². The reduction products of quinones are used as depigmenting agents.

The electrochemical behaviour of quinones in aprotic media has been studied extensively but most of the studies were devoted to understand the fundamental electrode process³. Anthraquinones were studied through potentiometry in various buffered media⁴. The electrochemical and ir spectroscopic properties of 9,10-anthraquinone in the low-temperature aluminium chloride (AlCl₃) and butylpyridinium chloride (BuPyCl) fused salt systems were studied as a function of melt acidity⁵. In the extensive literature dealing with the electrochemistry of quinones, there are several reports⁶, providing data in aprotic media, on compounds bearing hydroxyl group in positions conducive to hydrogen bonding to quinone oxygen. However, we have not come across any report in the literature related to the studies on electrochemical behaviour of 1-amino-9,10-anthraquinone (AAQ). Hence in the present investigation an attempt is made to study the electrochemical reduction behaviour of AAQ by using advanced electrochemical techniques. Differential pulse polarographic technique has also been specially employed for the analysis of the title compound.

Results and Discussion

AAQ is found to exhibit two well-defined waves/peaks in the entire pH range (Fig. 1) except in pH 2.0, where a single wave/peak is observed (Fig. 2), attributed to the reduction of quinone to hydroquinone in a direct two electron process. In the other case, the first wave/peak is attributed to the reduc-

Fig. 1 Typical d.c. polarogram of 1-amino-9,10-anthraquinone in pH 6.0, concn. = 0.5 mM, drop time = 3 s.

tion of the carbonyl group present at ninth position to the hydroxy group in one-electron process and the second to that of carbonyl group present at tenth position.

In cyclic voltammetry, two cathodic peaks C₁ and C₂ (Fig. 3) are observed in pH range 4.0–12.0 due to the reduction of carbonyl group at 9 and 10 position respectively to hydroxy groups. But an anodic peak (a₂) in the reverse scan has been noticed due to the oxidation of the 10-hydroxy group. The oxidation of 9-hydroxy group is not possible, because hydroxy group is involved in the hydrogen bond with the neighbouring NH₂ group.

The plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ and i_m vs $t^{3/8}$ are observed to be linear passing through origin in each of the supporting electrolytes employed, indicating adsor-

Fig. 2. Typical differential pulse polarogram of 1-amino-9,10-anthraquinone in pH 2.0; concn = 0.5 mM, drop time = 2 s.

tion-free and diffusion-controlled nature of the reduction process. In a.c. polarographic measurements, the depression of base current is not observed before and after the a.c. peak, also indicating the adsorption-free nature of the electrode reaction.

The first wave/peak reduction process from pH 4.0 to 12.0 is found to be irreversible and the second reversible as seen from the behaviour of reduction potentials with concentration, log-plot analysis, Tomes' criterion, comparison of a.c. polarographic summit potential from the d.c. polarographic half-wave potential, the relation of i_m vs $(1-\sigma)/(1+\sigma)$ and the absence of anodic peak in the reverse scan.

Fig. 3. Typical cyclic voltammogram of 1-amino-9,10-anthraquinone in pH 8.0; concn. = 0.5 mM; scan rate = 40 mV s⁻¹.

In pH 2.0 the reduction process is found to be reversible.

The $E_{1/2}$ and E_p values are found invariant with increase in pH of the buffer solution indicating the non-involvement of protons in the case of first wave/peak. But in the case of second wave/peak, the $E_{1/2}$ and E_p values are observed to show a regular increase in the negative direction with increase in pH of the buffer solution. This might be taken as indication for the protonated carbonyl group in position-10 of AAQ being electroactive in pHs 4.0 to 12.0. The number of proton involved in the rate-determining step is found to be one in pH 4.0–12.0 and two in pH 2.0.

Millicoulometry has been employed to determine the number of electrons in the electrode process and which is found to be two in pH 2.0 and one for the first and second waves in pH 8.0. The wave/peak heights observed are found to be almost equal in all the techniques in the entire pH range confirming the n value. Controlled potential elec-

TABLE I—KINETIC DATA FOR THE REDUCTION OF 0.5 mM AAQ IN 40% MeOH

pH of the supporting electrolyte	D.C. polarography Drop time = 3 s			Cyclic voltammetry Scan rate = 40 mV s ⁻¹			A.C. polarography Drop time = 3 s			Differential pulse polarography Drop time = 2 s		
	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	$-E_p$ V	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	$-E_s$ V	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹	$-E_m$ V	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹
2	0.24	8.30	—	0.24	9.55	—	0.24	10.60	—	0.24	11.16	—
4	(a) 0.25	8.91	1.66×10^{-6}	0.25	7.73	1.93×10^{-6}	0.26	9.27	1.48×10^{-6}	0.25	9.13	8.41×10^{-7}
	(b) 0.44	8.58	—	0.44	9.16	—	0.45	12.87	—	0.45	13.50	—
6	(a) 0.25	8.02	1.61×10^{-6}	0.25	7.31	1.64×10^{-6}	0.25	8.98	1.29×10^{-6}	0.25	8.69	8.23×10^{-7}
	(b) 0.55	6.51	—	0.56	8.17	—	0.55	12.13	—	0.56	11.70	—
8	(a) 0.25	7.55	1.53×10^{-6}	0.25	6.83	1.42×10^{-6}	0.26	9.76	1.12×10^{-6}	0.25	8.48	8.01×10^{-7}
	(b) 0.62	6.44	—	0.62	7.66	—	0.61	11.99	—	0.63	10.48	—
10	(a) 0.25	6.87	1.31×10^{-6}	0.25	6.43	1.16×10^{-6}	0.25	9.04	9.89×10^{-6}	0.25	8.11	7.43×10^{-7}
	(b) 0.70	7.70	—	0.70	8.62	—	0.71	12.43	—	0.71	11.24	—
12	(a) 0.26	6.53	1.27×10^{-6}	0.25	5.85	9.81×10^{-7}	0.25	8.99	9.68×10^{-6}	0.26	7.81	7.12×10^{-7}
	(b) 0.80	7.85	—	0.81	8.85	—	0.80	12.58	—	0.81	12.18	—

(a) = First wave/peak. (b) = Second wave/peak.

trollysis experiment carried out $E = -0.70$ V vs SCE in pH 8.0 for AAQ, is observed to give the corresponding hydroxy product which is confirmed by its spectral studies ($KBr, 3150\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Kinetic parameters such as transfer coefficient, diffusion coefficient and heterogeneous forward rate constant have been evaluated (Table 1). The adsorption-free nature of the electrode process is clearly evidenced from the nearly equal diffusion coefficient values are seen to gradually decrease, which accounts for the decrease in diffusion current with increase in pH due to non-availability of protons. The heterogeneous forward rate constant values for irreversible wave/peak are observed to be almost equal accounting for the constant reduction potential observed in pH range 4.0–12.0. This trend is particularly evident when the proton transfer is absent in the electrode process.

Based on the results obtained, the following reduction mechanism may be proposed for AAQ in different pH zones.

In pH ≤ 2

In $4 \leq \text{pH} \leq 12$.

Analysis : In the present investigation, differential pulse polarography has been employed for the quantitative estimation of AAQ using the calibration and standard addition methods. The optimum pH-range for obtaining well-resolved peaks for the quantitative determination of AAQ is pH 2.0. Using the calibration method, the peak height is found to be linear over the concentration range 1.0×10^{-4} to $1.5 \times 10^{-6} M$ and the lower detection limit is found to be $1.2 \times 10^{-6} M$ in pH 2.0 in 40% MeOH.

Recommended analytical procedure : A stock solution of AAQ ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) is prepared in the solvent MeOH. 1 ml of the standard solution is placed in a polarographic cell made up with 6 ml of supporting electrolyte of pH 10.0 and 3 ml of

MeOH. The solution is deaerated with oxygen-free nitrogen for 15 min and the polarogram is recorded. After taking the polarogram (peak potential = -0.71 V) small increments are added into the cell and deaerated for 2 min and then the polarogram is again recorded under identical conditions. The optimum conditions for the analytical determination in pH 10.0 are found to be drop time of 1 s and a pulse amplitude of 60 mV. The relative standard deviation is found to be 1.86% (10 replicants). The correlation coefficient is seen to be 0.9981.

Experimental

Metrohm polarecord E506 was used to record a.c. and differential pulse polarograms. Cyclic voltammograms were obtained by a Metrohm E 506 polarecord coupled with a E 612 VA scanner using a 2000 X-Y/t Digigraphic recorder. The hanging mercury drop of area of 0.02704 cm^2 was used as

working electrode in cyclic voltammetry. The dropping mercury electrode of area 0.02024 cm^2 was used as working electrode in differential pulse polarography and a.c. polarography. Ag/AgCl(s), Cl^- electrode was used as the reference electrode. D.C. Polarograms were recorded with a polarographic 364 analyser coupled with BD 8 Kipp and Zonen recorder. Platinum electrode served as the auxiliary electrode. All the experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Pure AAQ was used. Universal buffers of pH 2.0–12.0 were prepared by using 0.2 M boric acid, 0.05 M citric acid and 0.2 M trisodium orthophosphate (all AnalaR). The stock solution of AAQ was prepared in double-distilled methanol and

making up with the supporting electrolyte to obtain the desired concentration. Solution was purged with O₂-free N₂ for 15 min before the voltammograms was taken.

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